

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO TRAINING OF FUTURE ECONOMIC SPECIALISTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the professional competencies necessary for the implementation of innovative economic activities. Innovations are becoming increasingly important in today's rapidly developing global economy. To improve the competitiveness of countries and ensure economic growth, effective organization of innovative activities is necessary. It is in this process that expert economists play a major role. They must perform such important tasks as rapid adaptation to economic changes, the introduction of new technologies and the development of innovative approaches. Therefore, training economists for innovative activities, providing them with modern knowledge and skills is considered one of the pressing issues of our time.*

Keywords: *innovation, artificial intelligence, digital economy, blockchain, interdisciplinary education.*

It is known that nowadays the innovative activities are one of the important factors in ensuring economic development and competitiveness. Innovations include not only the creation and implementation of new technologies, but also the improvement of business processes, the efficient use of resources and the opening of new markets. Countries and enterprises can strengthen their positions in the global market by developing their products and services using modern technologies. At the same time, innovations such as big data and artificial intelligence are becoming increasingly important for optimizing economic processes, making quick decisions and paving the way to digital transformation. Innovative activity is the main source of sustainable development of the economies of countries.

It is important to suggest that economists play a decisive role in organizing and managing innovative activities. They are important participants in making strategic decisions on adapting to technological changes, creating new opportunities and effectively managing existing resources. Specialists must be able to anticipate market trends, be able to economically evaluate new technologies, be able to effectively direct financial and managerial resources necessary for the implementation of innovative projects. They are also of great importance in terms of developing new business models and strategies for achieving competitive advantages, assessing risks using economic analysis and developing an entrepreneurial culture.

It is worthy to note that the modern economy is closely linked to technological development, and the readiness of specialists actively involved in these processes is of great importance. The education system, especially in the field of economics, requires new, innovative approaches that depart from traditional methods of training personnel. International practice shows that training economic specialists in accordance with modern requirements largely depends on the content and methodology of education. From this point of view, several important factors should be taken into account in the educational process:

1. Educational programs adapted to technological changes. Today, when the economy is increasingly integrated with technology, economic experts need to be technologically literate.

Educational institutions should implement programs that teach big data analysis, artificial intelligence (AI), digital economy and blockchain technologies. According to a study by the McKinsey Global Institute, artificial intelligence technologies will increase global GDP by 13 trillion US dollars by 2030, which emphasizes the need for new economic specialists to understand and use these technologies.

2. Interdisciplinary educational approach. In the modern economy, economic knowledge alone is not enough to successfully implement innovations. The effectiveness of personnel training can be increased by including economics in the education system along with other subjects - for example, computer science, engineering and psychology. The importance of interdisciplinary education is that economic experts need to understand not only economic processes, but also innovations that arise at the intersection of different disciplines in the process of creating new products and services. For example, leading educational institutions such as the MIT Sloan School of Management prepare innovative economic personnel by combining economic programs with technology and design.

3. Project-based learning

Practical classes and project-based learning methods play an important role in the educational process in preparing specialists for innovative thinking. This gives students the opportunity to solve real economic problems. For example, Harvard Business School is a leader in developing skills for solving economic problems through project-based learning. Working on innovative projects, students acquire skills in strategic thinking, risk assessment and innovation implementation. This method not only strengthens students' theoretical knowledge, but also prepares them for real working conditions.

4. Development of startups and entrepreneurship

Special attention should be paid to entrepreneurship and startup activities in the training of economists. To succeed in an innovative economy, economists should have the opportunity not only to work at existing enterprises, but also to implement their own innovative projects and create startups. In particular, the Said Business School program at Oxford University trains expert economists in innovation, supporting entrepreneurship and startup projects. Mentoring, cooperation with startup accelerators and international financial institutions occupy a special place in this process.

5. Exchange of international experience to improve competitiveness.

In the context of globalization of the world economy, it is very important for economic experts to have international experience. Exchange of experience with international economic players, entering new markets and gaining knowledge on attracting foreign investment will have a positive impact on their professional development. Therefore, international educational exchange programs and cooperation with foreign universities should play a key role in training economic personnel. For example, international exchanges conducted within the framework of the Erasmus+ program allow students to better understand global trends in the innovative economy.

Conclusion

An educational system formed in accordance with the above requirements ensures the readiness of economic specialists for modern innovative activities. Forms of education combined with modern technologies, developing practical skills and supporting international cooperation play an important role in training competitive personnel for the economy of the future.

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